

Natural Language Processing Techniques for Product Matching of Web Scraping Ecommerce's

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Web Scraping of different retailers it's something personalized because each one code its own Ecommerce in a different way. Matching Products of different retailers have been a problem since Ecommerce where created. Different methods are evaluated and results are shown, comparing advantages and disadvantages of each one.

2. Aim

To evaluate the matching percentage of exactly the same products of different retailers with Natural Language Processing Techniques

3. Material and methods

A study was conducted testing different Natural Language Processing Techniques with over 130,000 products; considering a pipeline of data cleaning, data normalization and NLP Techniques. Each product can have different features like name, description, brand, provider, categories, ingredients, images, attributes

4. Results

Approximately 40,000 unique products where matched. Also very close products where added to a recommender system.

5. Conclusions

According to the results of this study, a combination of different Natural Language Processing techniques is improved a lot with the combination of Computer Vision with the images crawled. The pipeline of the data and the each technique is detailed in the body.

January 21, 2018

6. Keywords

Web Scraping, Natural Language Processing, Text Analytics, Semantics, Text Classification, Entity Recognition, AI, Corpus, Tagging, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Word Embeddings

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